

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXXIII. Dimeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with tetradentate and hexadentate azodye ligands

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Dimeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with a tetradentate ligand bis-[3-3'-di(*o*-hydroxyphenylazo)]-4,4'-dihydroxydinaphthalene having NO-ON donor set and a hexadentate ligand bis-[3-3'-di(phenylazo)]-4,4'-dihydroxydinaphthalene, having ONO-ONO donor set have been prepared. The complexes have been characterised by analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic spectral, ESR, NMR and X-ray diffraction data. The cobalt and nickel complexes are found to be octahedral, copper complexes are distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry has been assigned to Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

In continuation of our work¹ on inorganic polymer complexes of azodye and Schiff bases, we report herein the synthesis of dimeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with azodye ligands having NO-ON and ONO-ONO donor sets.

Results and discussion

The dimeric complexes synthesised have the compositions [M₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆], [M'₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂], [M₂L'(H₂O)₆] and [M'₂L'(H₂O)₂] where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}; LH₂ = bis-[3-3'-di(phenylazo)]-4,4'-dihydroxydinaphthalene and L'H₄ = bis-[3-3'-bis(*o*-hydroxyphenylazo)]-4,4'-dihydroxydinaphthalene. All the complexes have high melting points (>300°), amorphous in nature and insoluble in water and in most of the common organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and nitrobenzene but feebly soluble in dioxane, DMF and DMSO. Low molar conductance values (5.4–6.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

In the IR spectra of the ligands LH₂ and L'H₄, a broad band at 3435.1 and 3407.4 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of O-H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding and its absence in metal complexes indicates deprotonation of the phenolic protons and the bonding of the phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal ions². The bands at 1592.6 cm⁻¹ (LH₂) and 1592.4 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄) can be assigned to azo (-N=N-) vibration. The appearance of these bands at ~1589.0 and ~1587.4 cm⁻¹ respectively in the complexes suggest the bonding of the ligands to the metal ions through azo nitrogen atoms³. The bands observed at 1478.8 cm⁻¹ (LH₂) and at 1461.7 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄) can be assigned to ν_{C-O} vibration and its appearance in the complexes at ~1453.0 and ~1457.0 cm⁻¹

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic moment data of the complex

Compd.	Analysis (%):				μ _{eff} B.M.
	Found (Calcd.)				
	M	C	H	N	
LH ₂	–	77.6 (78.06)	3.8 (4.06)	10.9 (11.38)	–
L'H ₄	–	73.1 (73.58)	3.2 (3.45)	10.4 (10.73)	–
[Co ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	14.6 (14.94)	48.5 (48.71)	3.8 (4.06)	6.9 (7.10)	5.1
[Co ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	15.3 (15.75)	50.7 (51.37)	3.8 (4.01)	7.2 (7.49)	5.0
[Ni ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	14.4 (14.89)	48.3 (48.74)	3.9 (4.06)	6.8 (7.10)	3.0
[Ni ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	15.4 (15.70)	51.1 (51.40)	3.7 (4.01)	7.2 (7.49)	3.1
[Cu ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	15.5 (15.92)	47.9 (48.15)	3.6 (4.01)	7.0 (7.02)	3.1
[Cu ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	16.4 (16.78)	50.1 (50.75)	3.5 (3.96)	7.1 (7.40)	1.8
[Cd ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	26.7 (27.33)	45.8 (46.61)	2.9 (2.91)	6.5 (6.79)	–
[Cd ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	28.3 (28.76)	48.6 (49.04)	2.8 (2.81)	6.9 (7.15)	–
[Zn ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	17.5 (17.91)	52.4 (52.65)	3.2 (3.29)	7.3 (7.67)	–
[Zn ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	18.5 (18.97)	55.3 (55.78)	3.1 (3.19)	7.8 (8.13)	–
[Hg ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	39.6 (40.10)	38.2 (38.42)	2.4 (2.40)	5.3 (5.60)	–
[Hg ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	41.4 (41.81)	39.6 (40.06)	2.02 (2.29)	5.5 (5.84)	–

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the complexes

Compd.	Unit cell parameter	Density (g/cc)	<i>n</i>	Possible geometry
[Co ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	2θ = 25.00, 27.50, 29.38, 32.50, 35.00, 36.25, 39.06, 39.38, 45.00, 47.50, 48.56, 51.25, 53.33, 58.13, 60.22, 65.00, 67.50, 70.00, 73.13, 75.00, 77.50, 82.19, 85.00, 88.13, 92.00, 95.00, 98.13 A = 7.044, B = 12.093, C = 3.569, α = 90.00, β = 92.011, γ = 90.000, ν = 303.83	2.15	0.5	Monoclinic
[Co ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	2θ = 25.00, 26.50, 28.13, 30.00, 35.00, 37.50, 40.00, 42.50, 43.75, 45.00, 47.50, 48.56, 52.50, 55.00, 57.50, 48.56, 60.22, 61.88, 65.00, 68.44, 70.00, 76.88, 70.00, 77.50, 80.00, 82.50, 85.00, 87.50, 90.00, 92.50, 96.33, 97.50, 100.00 A = 8.130, B = 10.009, C = 7.105, α = 90.000, β = 114.373, γ = 90.000, ν = 526.61	2.35	1.0	Monoclinic

respectively indicates the coordination of the ligands to the metal ions through phenolic oxygen atoms. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the complexes is ascertained by the broad band at ~3507–3552 cm⁻¹ followed by small sharp peaks at 837.8–840.6 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations. The evidence of the bonding of the ligands is proved⁴ by the appearance at 417.8–420.0 cm⁻¹ (M–N) and 508.5–534.7 cm⁻¹ (M–O).

The μ_{eff} values of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to be ~5.1, 3.0 and 1.8 B.M. respectively indicating octahedral configuration⁵.

The ligand field bands of the cobalt complexes observed at 8075 (8120), 16200 (16300) and 19600 (20100) cm⁻¹ are assignable to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions respectively. The values of spectral parameters like D_q, B, β₃₅, ν₂/ν₁ and σ are found to be D_q = 812.5 (818.0) cm⁻¹, B = 771.7 (802.7), β₃₅ = 0.795 (0.827), ν₂/ν₁ = 2.006 (2.007), σ = 25.83 (20.98) respectively, providing further evidence for the octahedral stereochemistry of the cobalt complexes⁶. In case of nickel complexes, ligand field bands observed at 10110 (10120), 16895 (16920) and 24750 (24870) cm⁻¹ are assignable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions respectively in a distorted octahedral geometry. The ligand field parameters like D_q = 1011 (1012) cm⁻¹, B = 754.3 (762.0), β₃₅ = 0.725 (0.723), ν₂/ν₁ = 1.671 (1.672) and σ = 38.01 (36.63) suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes⁷. In the electronic spectra of copper complexes, one broad asymmetric band at ~13550–14750 cm⁻¹ with a maximum at 14365 (14370) cm⁻¹ could be attributed to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transitions in sup-

port of a distorted octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} ions⁸.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand LH₂ and L'H₄ were recorded in CDCl₃. The complex pattern observed at δ 6.7236–8.7316 (LH₂) and at δ 6.9203–8.3761 (L'H₄) corresponds to twenty and eighteen aromatic protons respectively. The phenolic protons of the ligands are beyond the range of the instrument.

The ESR spectra of the copper complex [Cu₂L(H₂O)₆] at X-band (RT) revealed the g_{av} value 2.0710. The covalent nature of M–L bond is indicated from the low g-value (<2.3). This value is in consistent with Cu–N and Cu–O bonded copper complex⁹.

The XRD study (powdered pattern) of the complexes [Co₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆] and [Co₂L'(H₂O)₆] were indexed and the unit cell parameters like A, B, C, α, β, γ and ν (volume) of the unit cell and d (density) have been calculated (Table 2). The calculated value of the n found to be 1/2 (half) for the former complex and 1 (one) for the latter complex, which agree well with the suggested structures of the complexes.

The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be four coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based on analytical, IR and conductance data.

The azodye LH₂ behaves as a tetradentate (bis-bidentate) ligand and L'H₄ as a hexadentate (bis-tridentate) ligand coordinated to the divalent ions through phenolic oxygen and azo nitrogen atoms forming dimeric complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. grade. The metal and nitrogen contents were estimated by standard methods¹⁰.

Conductivity measurements were made using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. The magnetic moments were measured at room temperature by Gouy method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded using IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M in DMF) using Hilger and Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer, ESR spectra on a E₄-spectrometer, NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX 400 in CDCl₃ and XRD (powder pattern) of the complexes have been recorded on a PW 1130/00 model X-ray diffractometer.

Preparation of the ligands :

The azodye ligands were prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from aniline (0.02 M, 1.86 g) and *o*-aminophenol (0.02 M, 2.18 g) with alkaline solution of di- α -naphthol (0.01 M, 2.90 g) at 0–5°.

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were reacted with ethanolic solution of the ligands in 2 : 1 molar ratio and the reaction mixture was then heated on a heating mantle at 60–70° for about 1 h. On cooling conc. ammonia was added dropwise with stirring till pH of the solution was raised to ~7. The solid compounds were then filtered, washed with

ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

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